

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

SOME ASPECTS OF IMPLICIT AND EXPLICIT FOREIGN LANGUAGE LEARNING

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Study in Support of Foreign Language Learning

Abstract

Learning foreign languages has always been a personal challenge because it requires a lot of effort and time. Foreign language learning involves acquiring knowledge and skills to communicate verbally and in writing. There are two main ways of learning a foreign language: implicit and explicit. Implicit and explicit language learning differ because implicit methodology involves learning through indirect rules and contextual understanding, while explicit methodology employs formulated rules and direct instruction. These two principal methods could be applied separately or together. This research aims to unravel the inherent mystery of how humans acquire a foreign language most easily and effectively, to accumulate the knowledge necessary for foreign language methodologists to create the most rational methodology for foreign language acquisition.

Keywords: foreign language acquisition; implicit learning through listening and reading comprehension; formal explicit instruction via teaching

1. Introduction

Mastery of any language has two degrees - spoken and written. There are two traditional ways of learning native and foreign languages. The difference between native and foreign language learning is that native language is learned by listening and speaking naturally, and written learning begins at a later stage - at school. Also, a foreign language can be understood in a similar way as native language learning, but it takes more time, and the learner must be surrounded by a foreign language environment, which is not available in most cases. The traditional way of learning a foreign language is academically, involving attending schools or courses. In the academic method, the foreign language is learned both spoken and written.

Interim conclusion: The native language is learned in two stages: spoken in the family and then written in school. The foreign language is usually studied at the same time - spoken and written in language courses, and the learners are often not in a foreign language environment, which is the reason for the difficulties.

2. Brain's Role in Foreign Language Communication

Perception, attention, and memory are faculties of the human brain that form the foundation of the human mind. Language serves as the conduit for human thoughts. While it is difficult to imagine how we can think without using language, in fact, it is possible. Although language is a powerful tool for organizing and expressing thoughts, there are various forms of thinking that do not rely on language, such as visual thinking, spatial reasoning, emotional processing, and procedural memory. Even though humans can think without using

language, we must consider language as part of human thinking, which is a broader concept. Ultimately, language serves as a human instrument for the expression of thoughts and communication.

The native language is embedded in the human mind, and people use it automatically. From a biological and physiological point of view, there is no difference between a native language and a foreign language. A foreign language is a second language, but in some circumstances, the second language can become the first language, meaning that it will be used automatically like the native language. Is it possible to learn a foreign language and speak it like our native language? Yes, it is possible. Then what are the obstacles? This issue concerns how we train our perception, attention, and memory to acquire a foreign language and use it automatically like a natural language. The key questions lay in how we use our brain faculties to learn foreign languages. The answers are what we must know about them to stimulate their proper activities in the best possible way to their maximum potential when we learn a foreign language.

Interim conclusion: The native language is spoken spontaneously (a kind of automaticity) without any effort, unlike a foreign language, which can also be spoken fluently like a mother tongue, provided it is mastered well enough.

3. Basic cognitive processes in foreign language acquisition

The word "cognitive" is derived from the Latin word "cognitio" which means "knowledge" or "recognition". In this context, "cognitive" refers to anything related to the processes of thinking, knowing, and understanding. So, when we talk about something like

"cognitive abilities" or "cognitive psychology," we're usually referring to those aspects of human functioning that include perception, thinking, remembering, problem-solving, and so on. So, the main meaning of "cognitive" is related to the processes of understanding and thinking.

Nejati, V., (2023) Perception, attention, and memory are basic cognitive processes that play a key role in learning a foreign language. In the intricate process of language communication, the brain orchestrates a complex interplay of sensory input, perception, attention, and memory. These cognitive functions play pivotal roles in shaping our ability to comprehend and produce language effectively.

Beginning with sensory input, the brain receives auditory and visual information, which serves as the

foundation for language processing. Perception involves interpreting this sensory input, distinguishing linguistic stimuli, and comprehending their meaning. Attention then directs cognitive resources towards relevant linguistic content, facilitating focused processing and comprehension. Memory plays a critical role in language communication by retrieving linguistic knowledge, vocabulary, and contextual information stored in long-term memory. This enables us to understand and produce language accurately and fluently.

As linguistic information is processed, the brain generates appropriate responses based on the integrated sensory input, perceptual processing, attentional focus, and memory retrieval. This culminates in effective language comprehension and production, whether through spoken or written communication. (fig. 1)

Figure 1

Throughout this process, the brain operates within various models of information processing, including serial, parallel, and cascade. These models illustrate the dynamic and interconnected nature of cognitive functions during language processing, shaping our ability to navigate linguistic interactions seamlessly. [1]

a. Perception

Perception refers to the acquisition of visual and audio inputs from the environment.

(Shatil, E., Thompson, H.J. 2011) Definition: Perception is the ability to capture, process, and actively make sense of the information that our senses receive. It is the cognitive process that makes it possible to interpret our surroundings with the stimuli that we receive through sensory organs.

Perception is how we understand and make sense of the world around us using our senses. It's about taking in information through our eyes, ears, and other senses, and then figuring out what it means. This ability helps us navigate our daily lives by allowing us to interpret what's happening around us. We can get better at perception with practice, like doing puzzles or playing memory games. It involves both taking in what's

happening around us and using our expectations and previous experiences to understand it better.

- Perception helps us understand the world around us. It's split into five main senses:

- Sight: Seeing and understanding light that comes into our eyes. The back of our brain, called the occipital lobe, handles this.

- Hearing: Listening and understanding sounds that come into our ears. The temporal lobe in our brain helps with this.

- Touch: Feeling and understanding pressure and movement on our skin. The parietal lobe in our brain deals with this.

- Smell: Recognizing scents in the air. The olfactory bulb and piriform cortex in our brain help with this.

- Taste: Understanding flavors from things we eat and drink. Specific areas in our brain control this, like the G1 and G2 areas.

- In addition to the five basic senses, there are other types of perception:

- Spatial: Knowing where you are, things around you and your own body. It's linked to touch and movement awareness.

- Shape: Understanding the outline and details of objects. It's connected to sight and touch.
- Balance: Feeling gravity's pull and keeping steady. It's tied to hearing.
- Temperature: Feeling hot or cold on your skin. It's part of touch.
- Pain: Sensing extreme temperatures or harmful chemicals. It's also part of touch.
- Itch: Feeling something on your skin that makes you want to scratch. It's also part of touch.
- Body awareness: Knowing where your body parts are and how they're positioned. It's linked to balance and touch.
- Internal feelings: Sensing what's going on inside your body.
- Time: Understanding how things change over time.
- Movement: Knowing how things move and how fast. It's linked to sight, space, time, touch, internal feelings, body awareness, and balance.
- Taste: Recognizing strong flavors in your mouth.
- Magnetic fields: Sensing information from magnetic fields, like some animals do. It's more advanced in animals like pigeons, but humans might have some ability too.

- All kinds of reception are important for speaking any language, but it's very important auditory perception and vision perception:

- Auditory perception is how we understand sounds. When the phone rings and you hear your mom's voice, your brain quickly deciphers her words and emotions. This involves specialized brain areas for hearing. To understand sound:

1. Sound reaches your ears: Vibrations, like voices, create waves that reach your inner ear.

2. Signals travel: Cells in your ear send signals through different brain parts to the thalamus.

3. Brain processes sound: The auditory cortex in your brain's temporal lobes processes sound, helping you understand it.

- Visual perception is the brain's way of making sense of what we see. It's a complex process involving various brain parts specialized in vision. It starts with light hitting the retina in our eyes, then travels through the optic nerve to the brain's visual cortex in the occipital lobe. [2]

The first step of foreign language perception is its reception. The initial stage in perceiving a foreign language involves receiving or taking in the language, likely through listening or reading. This reception of the language is fundamental before further processing, understanding, or production of the language can occur. The input of foreign language comes from what we listen and read, so it is important for the study materials to be of high quality. When the learner practices listening comprehension, the sound of the material must be very pleasant to be perceived without difficulty that would disturb and hinder his attention. This is achieved by using quality recordings of sound materials, also by using quality audio-visual equipment. The same applies to written materials, which must also be pleasing to the eye to receive them without unnecessary distraction from their content.

Interim conclusion: Quality reception of input information and a high degree of perception are the first crucial steps to foreign language acquisition.

b. Attention

Attention is the ability to focus on certain aspects of language or situations.

(Perets, C., Demiris, G., Reeder, 2011) Definition: Attention is the cognitive process that makes it possible for people to position themselves towards relevant stimuli and consequently respond to them. This cognitive ability is very important and is an essential function in our daily lives. Luckily, attention can be trained and improved with the appropriate cognitive training.

Attention is about picking out and focusing on important things. It helps us direct ourselves toward what matters and react to it. This ability is crucial for daily life, but the good news is, we can get better at it with the right training.

- Attention is a vital process we use daily. Scientists found it's not just one thing but a bunch of different parts. According to Sohlberg and Mateer's model, attention has these parts:

1. Arousal Attention: How awake and alert we are.

2. Focused Attention: How well we can focus on one thing.

3. Sustained Attention: Keeping focused for a long time.

4. Selective Attention: Focusing on one thing despite distractions.

5. Alternating Attention: Switching focus between different things.

6. Divided Attention: Paying attention to multiple things at once.

Each sense has its part of the brain that helps us make sense of what we experience.

- Examples of Attention

- When we drive, we use all our attentional skills. We stay alert, focus on the road, avoid distractions, switch lanes, and handle all driving tasks at once.

- Attention is crucial for studying. You need to be awake and focused on what you're learning. Sustained attention helps you study for long periods without getting bored or forgetting.

- Attention matters in every job, from office work to air traffic control. Every profession needs different types of attention.

- In daily life, we pay attention to everything from cooking to socializing. Without it, we might forget what we're doing, like throwing a spoon in the trash or putting an empty carton in the fridge. [3]

The human brain does not function like a tape recorder or a photo camera, recording information indefinitely. When learning a foreign language, input can be received through listening or reading attentively. However, mere exposure is insufficient for effective memorization. Information must be assimilated, meaning it needs to be deeply understood, which requires significant attention. This process can be enhanced by seeking alternative meanings, synonyms, solutions, or applications of the studied language unit. Consequently, the focus on learning intensifies, leading to a greater likelihood of permanent memorization. Foreign language learners should prioritize comprehending the meaning

of what they hear or read. Only through this active engagement and attention can they truly internalize the information and commit it to memory. Ultimately, only well-understood and assimilated information can evolve into genuine knowledge stored in the human brain.

Interim conclusion: Focusing on learning material with great attention is necessary for the information to be assimilated and transformed into knowledge that can remain in the human mind. Maintaining sustained attention throughout the learning process enhances comprehension and retention.

c. Memory

Memory is used to store and retrieve information, such as new words and grammar rules. These processes are the basis of learning new language knowledge and skills.

Definition: Memory is the brain's capacity to store information and recall it when necessary. It enables us to remember facts, ideas, emotions, connections between concepts, and other past experiences. Although the hippocampus plays a central role in memory, memories aren't localized to a specific brain region; rather, multiple brain areas are involved. Ageing often affects memory, but cognitive training and various brain exercises can help improve it.

- Memory is a complex brain function that's crucial in daily life. It involves various brain parts and has different types. Here's how we can divide it:

1. Based on how long information stays in our mind:

- Sensory memory holds data for a few seconds.

- Short-term memory, working memory, and long-term memory store information for longer periods. Long-term memory can keep things for a very long time.

2. Based on the type of information:

- Verbal memory deals with words we hear or read.

- Non-verbal memory handles everything else, like images and feelings.

3. Based on the sense involved:

- Visual memory for what we see.

- Auditory memory for what we hear.

- Olfactory memory for smells.

- Gustatory memory for tastes.

- Haptic memory for touch sensations.

- How does your brain remember stuff?

To remember even simple things like what you did yesterday, your brain goes through a few steps. Each step is important for remembering things right. Here are the phases:

1. Coding: This step happens when you take in information, like when you meet someone unknown and learn their name. You must pay attention to remember it later.

2. Storage: To keep what you learn; your brain stores it in your memory. For example, you remember the name and link it to the person's face.

3. Retrieval: When you need to remember something, your brain digs into its storage and brings it back. So, the next time you see the person, you remember their name.

- Memory helps you remember lots of things:

1. Personal stuff like your home address, your parents' names, and your friends' faces.

2. Daily details like what you ate yesterday or the capital of your country.

3. Work-related info like meeting schedules, client names, and computer passwords.

4. School stuff like exam dates and plans with friends.

5. Practical things like driving routes, where you parked, and even how to drive. [4]

Human memory maintains the knowledge by the production of human brain energy called adenosine triphosphate (ATP), a molecule that carries energy for its various functions.[5]

Focusing attention on certain foreign language units supplies them with the energy necessary for retention in the brain. Permanent retention of foreign language knowledge is possible by additional energy supply which can be done by refreshment of memory or in other words by more attention to the knowledge.

Interim conclusion: Retention of certain knowledge in the human brain is possible by an additional supply of brain energy by paying special attention to this knowledge itself.

d. Stages of reception, perception, assimilation of incoming foreign language information, and its transformation into sustainable knowledge

- Receiving information (INPUT information) is the first step in foreign language learning. It is a technical factor related to the physical quality of the foreign language information received by the learner. Information can be acquired through listening and reading. If the quality of the sound and written text for reading is poor, the learner may become distracted by background noise or the unappealing nature of the reading material.

- Perception of received information: At this stage, the most important thing is to focus on receiving foreign language information. The recipient's concentration determines the actual percentage of information received. Fatigue, distraction, and a bad mood have a negative impact. When learners' attention is poor and the physical quality of the received information is low, then the percentage of its perception will also be low.

- Assimilation of received information and its transformation into knowledge: The received information must be assimilated. For this purpose, it is necessary to understand it; information that is too difficult to understand will have a low rate of assimilation.

- Remembering knowledge: Remembering the learned information depends on the time spent on understanding and assimilating it. It also depends on its complexity and quantity. Periodically activating knowledge is necessary to keep it up-to-date and prevent loss or forgetfulness.

- Speaking and writing in foreign languages (OUTPUT information) are the best ways to maintain and improve fluency in a foreign language.

Interim conclusion: The primary function of the human brain is to receive information in a foreign language, perceive it, assimilate it, and convert it into

knowledge, which needs to be periodically activated to prevent loss. Additionally, language practice is essential for maintaining proficiency in a foreign language.

4. Implicit and Explicit Ways of Foreign Language Teaching and Learning

a. Introduction

Ellis, N., (2021) Ellis, N., (2021) Implicit and explicit foreign language learning are two distinct processes that influence human cognitive capabilities. Implicit learning occurs naturally and without conscious operations, while explicit learning is more conscious and involves making and testing hypotheses. Knowledge attainment can occur implicitly, explicitly through selective learning, or explicitly via given rules. The acquisition of a first language (L1) depends on natural meaningful communication and innate linguistic abilities.

Some experts in second language teaching methods, such as the Audiolingual and Natural approach, argue that learning second languages is like learning first languages (L1) and reject explicit grammar-based instruction. However, adolescents and adults can still learn rules and grammar patterns. Traditional L2 teaching, such as Grammar Translation and Cognitive Code, heavily relies on rule-based methods. To determine the best method, there is a need for a detailed theoretical analysis of explicit and implicit learning processes, understanding the representations and interrelations of explicit and implicit memory, and applying linguistic analyses to different performance types and learner types. [6]

R. Ellis presents his theory of instructed second language (L2) acquisition, focusing on the acquisition and use of implicit and explicit knowledge. He distinguishes between these two types of knowledge and discusses the relationship between them, the automatization of L2 knowledge, and the role of another knowledge. Ellis believes that explicit knowledge plays a significant role in L2 acquisition, facilitating the processes of noticing and comparing linguistic features. He also sees benefits in output practice, which allows both explicit and implicit knowledge to become automatized.

Interim conclusion: Implicit learning is the acquisition of knowledge about the underlying structure of a complex stimulus environment by a process which takes place naturally, simply and without conscious operations. Explicit learning is a more conscious operation where the individual makes and tests hypotheses in a search for structure.

b. Comparative analysis between Implicit and Explicit Second Language

Hulstijn, J.H. (2005) Comparing and analyzing implicit and explicit learning in second language acquisition (SLA) is crucial for both theoretical and educational reasons. The differential success in one's first language (L1) and second language (L2) is a central issue in SLA theory. Theories include brain maturation, brain adaptation processes, access to Universal Grammar, L1 interference, and sociopsychological factors. Some scholars argue that L1 acquisition relies on implicit learning processes, while L2 acquisition often relies on both. The extent to which implicit and explicit learning can explain the differential success of SLA is likely to determine their relevance for L2 instruction. Curriculum planners, material designers, teachers, and learners all have a vested interest in knowing which linguistic domains L2 learning best benefit from implicit or explicit learning modes might.[7]

c. Implicit and Explicit Instruction via Teaching

Ellis, R. (2009) Instruction means teaching someone how to do something. There are two main types of instruction: indirect and direct. Indirect instruction helps learners learn by doing activities in the language they are learning. For example, a task-based lesson where students talk to each other in the new language. Direct instruction is when teachers tell students exactly what they need to learn. This often follows a set plan, like teaching specific grammar rules.

Implicit and explicit instruction are two ways of teaching, but they don't always match up with indirect and direct instruction. Implicit instruction is when students learn something without realizing it. They pick up rules or patterns while focusing on other things, like the meaning of what they're saying. It's like learning something without directly studying it.

Explicit instruction is more straightforward. It involves teaching students a rule directly and making them aware of it. This can happen by explaining the rule or helping students figure it out from examples. So, implicit instruction is more like indirect teaching, and explicit instruction is like direct teaching. (fig. 2)

Implicit teaching happens when students learn naturally through tasks, without focusing on grammar rules. For example, if students talk to each other in a foreign language, they might pick up grammar without trying.

Explicit teaching is more direct. It can happen when teachers correct students' mistakes (reactive) or explain grammar rules before doing activities (proactive).

Figure 2

Implicit and explicit teaching can happen naturally during tasks or with direct explanations from teachers. It's important to know that when we talk about implicit and explicit instruction, we're looking at it from the teacher's point of view. However, when we talk about implicit and explicit learning, it's from the student's point of view. They might not always match up.

The two types of transfer of knowledge and skills, called implicit teaching and explicit teaching, can in principle be carried out completely separately, as well as in combination with a different ratio between them. There are knowledge and skills that are highly complex and require mandatory explicit teaching, and conversely, there are quite a few skills that a person can acquire in an implicit way. These two theoretical names

can be equated to the widely known and used concepts of theory and practice.

So, just because a teacher teaches something directly doesn't mean the student will learn it that way. And sometimes, students learn things without the teacher explicitly teaching them. Also, the goal of explicit teaching isn't just for students to know things directly; it's also for them to understand them without thinking too much about it. [8]

d. Authors hypothesis on Implicit and Explicit Native and Foreign Language Learning

In terms of Native and Foreign language learning, both methods have specific applications. When learning the spoken native language, the implicit method is applied, and when learning it in writing, it is the opposite, and the explicit method is applied. (fig. 3)

Types of Processes for Learning of a Native Language

Figure 3

Children learn their mother tongue in a family environment through interaction with their parents. As children reach a certain age and their minds mature, they typically begin attending school, where they learn the language grammatically in their native tongue.

Interim conclusion: Spoken native language is acquired implicitly, while written native language and grammar are acquired explicitly.

When learning a foreign language, the application of the two methods is different and depends on the specific foreign language as well as the conditions in which

it will be studied. If the mother tongue and the foreign language are from the same language group, for example, the group of Slavic or Romance languages, then it is reasonable that the oral acquisition begins for a short period with the explicit method, then continues with the implicit method, while the written acquisition will be in an explicit way, like the acquisition of the native language. If the mother tongue and the foreign language are from different language groups, then it is reasonable to start the oral and written acquisition of the foreign language using the explicit method for a relatively longer period. (fig. 4)

Types of Processes for Learning of a Foreign Language

Figure 4

After mastering the basic grammar level of the foreign language with reasonable minimum vocabulary, it is wise to apply the implicit method, consisting mainly of listening comprehension and reading comprehension, in parallel with the explicit method if it is necessary. After a complete study of the grammar of the foreign language, it is reasonable to proceed only with the implicit method. If the foreign language learner is surrounded by the environment of the language being studied, then it is reasonable to apply implicit and explicit learning to be carried out with an intensity consistent with the desired goals to be achieved in connection with the acquisition of the foreign language.

Conclusion:

Learning a foreign language is a complex and time-consuming process that requires a significant amount of time and effort. Achieving quick and high-quality results in learning foreign languages, as well as maintaining proficiency, is crucial for the work undertaken. Acquisition of a foreign language can occur naturally, through a method known as the implicit method, or through organized instruction with a teacher, known as explicit methods. Language proficiency encompasses both oral and written skills, as well as passive and active use. The foreign language may belong to a different language group than one's native language. Foreign language learners may find themselves in environments with native speakers or without. Each of these scenarios requires a tailored approach to language learning. This is accomplished through the proper application of two methods: the implicit method, which involves listening and reading comprehension, and the explicit method, which involves instruction from teachers applied in a systematic manner.

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